

Report on the PCRS data forum meeting 31st August 2018

Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland

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Executive summary

- This report summarises discussions from the PCRS data forum meeting held on 31st August 2018 to consider access to the PCRS data.
- Different systems of access are necessary for different levels of data (i.e. aggregate-level anonymised data versus individual-level pseudonymised data).
- Open access to anonymised data is seen as desirable and would ideally include the maximum amount of information that can be safely and appropriately released publicly.
- The public and patients play an important role and should be involved in governance processes. Clear communication is vital to ensure public trust.
- As well as use of the data for research, it can play a role in direct clinical care as well as quality improvement and health system monitoring.
- Anonymisation and pseudonymisation of the data would be carried out by the PCRS, however other roles, including linkage, could be carried out by other bodies. There are advantages and disadvantages to locating these functions within or outside of the health system.
- Appropriate contractual and legal protections could apply to all levels of the data, including open data.
- Governance procedures could include a committee to approve requests to access certain levels of the data. The place of research ethics committees and the Health Research Consent Declaration Committee in this context needs to be considered.
- The sustainability of the system should be underpinned by central funding provided to national bodies to support this work.

Background

A meeting was held at the HRB Centre for Primary Care Research, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, in collaboration with colleagues from the Primary Care Reimbursement Service (PCRS) on 31st August 2018. The purpose of the meeting was to provide a forum to discuss access to PCRS pharmacy reported data that will enable enhanced use of PCRS data for quality improvement, patient safety and research purposes throughout Ireland. The PCRS is responsible for payments to general practitioner, pharmacy, and dental contractors who provide health services on behalf of the state. In relation to medicines, pharmacies submit claims on a monthly basis to the PCRS for prescribed medicines that they dispense under the community drug schemes. This data is processed by the PCRS for the purposes of reimbursement, however it also represents a rich resource for evaluation and research which may be conducted or stimulated by a wide range of organisations including the PCRS itself.

Over 40 stakeholders from universities, state agencies, and the PCRS attended the meeting (attendee names have been included as Appendix 1). An introduction from Professor Tom Fahey (RCSI) was followed by three presentations outlining different use cases of the PCRS data (i.e. different levels of data) illustrated by examples of previous research. The following levels of data were presented:

1. Including patient identifier for linkage to other data sources where explicit patient consent (and patient identifier) has been obtained separately for the use of PCRS data.
2. No patient identifier e.g. aggregate data at GP practice, regional, or national level.
3. Including a patient identifier which cannot be linked where no explicit consent has been obtained separately.
4. Including patient identifier for linkage to other data sources where no explicit consent has been obtained separately.

Ivan McConkey (PCRS) presented an outline of the PCRS's objective and proposed principles for data sharing. The forum then moved to group discussions at tables of approximately 10 people. For approximately 45 minutes, groups discussed three questions:

1. *What would an ideal system and process of access to PCRS data look like?*
2. *What are the important governance procedures that such a system would need? e.g. Approval, Privacy, Data protection.*
3. *How can this access system be funded to ensure sustainability?*

Each table had a facilitator as well as a note taker who documented discussions. Following the end of the group discussions, each group was invited to feedback their key points on each question to the wider meeting and the forum was then opened for comments, questions and discussion. These discussions were also noted.

The notes from the individual group discussions and wider group discussion were summarised and organised across common topics that emerged. This summary of discussions is presented below.

PCRS forum discussion summary

System of Access

Different solutions required

In the context of the four use cases outlined, the group discussed that different solutions will be necessary for different levels of data. A tiered system of access which has increasingly strict requirements for access based on the level of detail of the data was proposed. This could range from publicly available data (fully anonymised or data aggregated by WHO Anatomical Therapeutic Classification (ATC) code or at geographical/prescriber level) available to pull down from the HSE Open Data platform, to a middle level of access which researchers can request for specific research studies (individual level and full ATC codes), to access requiring data linkage without patient consent to other data sources. In the latter case, there would be a need for third party involvement for linkage.

Open data simplifies governance issues

The proposal for open publicly available anonymised data may simplify a number of considerations. For example, there would be few issues with governance (in contrast to studies requiring third party linkage) and this could be done without large shifts in establishing appropriate bodies and with relatively little in the way of resource requirements (e.g. one full time person). A system of open access to a certain level of data would be very beneficial if it allowed for data files to be pulled down/downloaded for analysis etc. and made available in an appropriate file format such as .csv.

Contents of data and method of access

There was some consensus that what the data contains should be as broad as possible. The maximum amount of information that can be safely and appropriately released publicly should be. It should ideally accommodate different requirements of research studies/evaluations. Where it is possible for patients in a specific study to provide consent for linkage, there should be a facility for logging linked PCRS data for these longitudinal studies over time. For anonymous data made publicly available, there should be an efficient system for access.

The importance of a data dictionary was emphasised, with different dictionaries for the various levels of data and that there should be consultation with interested parties on what data elements are most useful for example, medication ATC code, patient age group and gender.

There was some discussion relating to aggregating data to avoid identification in “anonymised” data, for example in individual-level data where few patients are on a certain medication. The processing of data to do this for rare drugs while leaving more detail for all others would have to be considered, however this likely represents a very small proportion of medications.

For longitudinal studies and linkage studies, it is important that consistent identifiers are generated which span across time periods and data sources to allow for retrospective and prospective studies. This may be facilitated by the rollout of the Individual Health Identifier. It was emphasised that the PCRS data is not prescribing data per se, but rather represents dispensing data. As the Individual Health Identifier (IHI) is

rolled out with other national eHealth initiatives such as electronic prescribing, this distinction may become more important as linkage becomes increasingly feasible.

Public and patients

Across all topics, the role of patients and the public were discussed. The system in Scandinavian countries where all data across national registries can be linked using unique identifiers was mentioned as an ideal or exemplar, however this has taken decades of culture change to progress and be accepted by citizens.

There is a balance of risks (of identifiability or data breaches) and benefits (of research to improve health or evaluation to improve the health system) that is weighed up in the decision of how much the population are prepared to share. There is generally good buy-in from patients for the use of their data for the purpose of clinical care, and experience from other research studies like TILDA is people are generally willing to provide consent for linkage to address important health research questions. Therefore for future studies where possible, getting direct patient consent is the best option both for data protection reasons and fostering trust.

In other countries, there is good progress and buy in for data linkage for direct care and research, but inevitably some members of public will look to opt-out. In Scotland, there is a register of research projects which patients can consent to on a project by project basis. There may be a need to go there slowly, by showing credibility and benefit. This could be a generational effort to bring the public on board but at the same time we cannot wait around for this to be achieved. There should be appropriate public consultation and awareness and information about the system and legislation relating to data and data linkage in order to foster public approval for passing of legislation and avoid public disapproval.

It is important that any governance procedures or approvals for access have appropriate public representatives and involvement. Often patients can be happier to provide consent than, for example, ethics committees anticipate.

Purposes

The use of the PCRS data for many purposes was discussed. This includes in direct clinical care, for example in outcomes based assessment (i.e. with real time availability of data could detect asthma exacerbations based on new prescriptions) or to assist with medicines reconciliation. The time-lag may make this use challenging given the current format of the PCRS data but it represents the best current source of such information. With the development of other resources, such as ePrescribing and the summary card record, this may provide superior sources of prescribed/dispensed medications information.

Although the discussion focussed predominantly on research, analysis for accountability in prescribing and quality measurement was also highlighted. This is currently done in England where the NHS make practice-level prescribing data available and openprescribing.net has been developed as a platform to analyse and display this data. This kind of information is required for managing and monitoring of health system, measuring quality, and can demonstrate the value of secondary use and open access in improving health system performance.

Depending on the level of data made available, this raised questions regarding general practitioner and pharmacist consent, such as whether consent is required if data is provided with identifiable GP practices or pharmacies. The potential to assess the quality of health professionals' prescribing for public accountability

and quality improvement was discussed. While some viewed this as a desirable outcome, the need for governance around this along with a culture shift and engagement with the professions and public was emphasised because of the implications for GPs/pharmacists. Not all groups viewed this use of the data positively.

Roles

The roles and responsibilities of various bodies in any system were discussed. Data made available would need to be fully anonymised and the PCRS would be responsible for such data manipulation to ensure compliance with data protection legislation. There are a number of technical ways that this could be done (i.e. a database with hashed identifiers with an application programming interface (API) to run a query to pull the relevant data) but that this should have a sound legislative basis. Regardless, it is a challenge for the PCRS to respond to researcher requests for data.

For linkage studies, a trusted third party may be needed to pseudonymise the data and link to additional data sources. It was felt that in the longer term a dedicated government agency may be needed with appropriate funding, skills and expertise to perform trusted third party functions nationally.

The fact that public money is used to fund our current siloed data collection functions was cited as a reason to make these functions more linked and increase the value this information could provide. It was unclear what existing body would be best placed to fulfil this role, in contrast to some other countries with national health informatics bodies. The Health information strategy 2001 identified HIQA as suitable for such a role, however their function has changed somewhat in the intervening period and this needs systematic full time commitment. The importance of a body having expertise, a good reputation, and credibility to fulfil this function was emphasised.

There was some disagreement about where this function should be located. This function could be fulfilled by the CSO given the expertise and experience in the area however this would require increased capacity and a statutory basis with the proposals contained in the HRB's DASSL model (Data Access Storage Sharing Linkage)¹. An argument was made that given research should feed in to clinical care and the health system, that it should be in or very closely linked to health services with input from research community/universities. This would ensure it meets the requirements of the health service. A counter argument was that expertise/credibility exists in other sectors and that data linkage issues did not just concern health with similar challenges existing across government. Hence it may be more attractive to have reports feeding back in to the health system from outside. This could include independence in governance from the health system and the interests of users of this health care evaluation data.

Protections

There was much consideration about appropriate legislation and protection relating to all levels of data. A proportional and balanced approach which considers patients' right to data protection and privacy is key. This could include a policy with different levels of access supported by contractual arrangements. Protections are important to prevent malicious use, data breaches, and reputational damage to the bodies involved. Good management of the data access is vital to protect trust of the public. The systems must also

¹ Moran R (2016) Proposals for an Enabling Data Environment for Health and Related Research in Ireland. Health Research Board in Ireland, Dublin, Ireland

be coherent with the new data information policy and legislative framework i.e. the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Data Protection Act 2018 (Health Research) Regulations 2018. This means the need for a data controller that accepts risk of different levels of access. Similarly, if the data protection commissioner endorses and signs off on the process, this would provide reassurance.

For anonymised data made available through the Open Data portal, this should be assessed with respect to the Data Protection Act 2018 (Health Research) Regulations although the initial feeling is that it was compliant. The processing of personal data in order to anonymise it for sharing by the PCRS needs a clear legislative basis, so that consent is not the legal basis for processing. The PCRS does provide fair notice of planned processing to patients.

An open system does not mean there are no protections. This data would be licensed appropriately so users would commit not to identify individuals (based on medications) or attempt to link to other sources. Much like in Scandinavian countries, the penalties for intentionally breaching such contracts or other data protection laws ought to be very severe, and such penalties for data breaches are mandated under GDPR. The PCRS could also implement a registration system which allows monitoring of who is accessing the data. The system should also guard against inappropriate analysis or use of the data for casual query and ensure responsible use of data (e.g. journalism) and that those analysing it understand the data.

Governance

The group discussed governance system in place relating to other sources of research data. The group discussed the potential for a governance committee to consider and approve access based on individual data requests for different research projects. Approvals may only be required for certain levels of data access and any such committee should have public and patient involvement. Further consideration of how this fits in the context of research ethics committee approvals and consent declarations from the new Health Research Consent Declaration Committee is required. This is also a time of change for ethics committees as they will no longer be granting consent exemptions.

Other suggestions included a transparency in the process of applying for data access, and a reasonable timeframe for receiving a response and receiving the data (ideally in the range of 4-6 weeks). This is important for how current the data may be. There should be openness regarding the application form, data dictionary (for different levels of data), and user guidance/FAQs to support applications. Governance procedures should also allow for specific linkage for organisations that have legislative basis to collect data without consent (e.g. NCRI) and guard against commercial use, which would likely erode public trust.

Sustainability

The management and monitoring of the system requires appropriate resourcing, and this requirement increases with greater complexity of the data. The group discussed the potential for two strands of funding. Firstly, central or core funding provided to national bodies to support this work. Secondly, the options of financial costs to researchers to supplement this were considered.

It was emphasised that this should not be seen as paying for or selling patient data, but rather recouping/cost-recovery for the funding required. It was suggested public anonymised data available through Open Data should not attract any fee. In Scotland and Wales, basic costs are recouped from individual research projects for work done in preparing data sets on a specific project basis. The UK Clinical

Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) similarly has an application fee. There could also be a higher cost if researchers are applying for grant money, contingent on the grant being successfully awarded, however the potential for a fee to represent a financial barrier to worthwhile research being conducted should also be considered. Any such system may require a phased process of payment, where it is funded for a 2-year period for instance through the HRB, Dept of Health, or leveraging off existing systems in order to gauge how many people would be applying and likely revenue. For linkage studies, a mechanism to combine resources across relevant organisations could reduce the cost of access. The National Cancer Registry Ireland is a good example of sustainability in terms of their public role.

Appendix 1. Meeting attendees

Roisin Adams
Fiachra Bane
Joe Barry
Kathleen Bennett
Leonard Browne
Gerard Bury
Cathal Cadogan
Alan Cahill
Caitriona Cahir
Claire Collins
Derek Corrigan
Gráinne Cousins
Conan Donnelly
Berni Dunne
Tom Fahey
Liam Glynn
Tamasine Grimes
Trish Harrington
John Hayden
Anne Marie Hoey
Patricia Kearney
Ciara Kirke
MaryJo MacAvin
Anthony Macken
Teresa Maguire
Ivan McConkey
Frank Moriarty
Kate Mulvenna
Muiris O'Connor
Kevin O'Flanagan
Muriel Pate
Jan Rigby
Aileen Sheehy
Niall Sinnott
Susan Smith
Álmath Spooner
Austin Stack
Anthony Staines
Niall Turner
Mary Walsh
Cathal Walsh
David Williams